

APPENDIX: MATHEMATICAL PROOFS

Proof of Theorem 1

Proof of Theorem 1. We prove the statement by contradiction. Therefore, let T be a phylogenetic X -tree, and let π_T be a strict and reversible ranking for T with respect to $X' \subset X$ and induced subtree \tilde{T} on taxon set \tilde{X} . Moreover, let $c = [x_i, x_j]$ be a cherry of T and assume that $\{x_i, x_j\} \cap X' = \emptyset$, i.e. $x_i, x_j \notin X'$. Note that by definition, we have

$$FP_T(x_i) = \sum_{e \in P(T; \rho, x_i)} \frac{\lambda_e}{D_e}$$

and, analogously,

$$FP_T(x_j) = \sum_{e \in P(T; \rho, x_j)} \frac{\lambda_e}{D_e}.$$

Now note that as x_i and x_j form a cherry with some parent w , the paths $P(T; \rho, x_i)$ and $P(T; \rho, x_j)$ are identical except for the last edges, i.e. except for the pendant edges, say $e_i = (w, x_i)$ and $e_j = (w, x_j)$. This immediately implies

$$FP_T(x_i) = FP_T(x_j) - \frac{\lambda_{e_j}}{D_{e_j}} + \frac{\lambda_{e_i}}{D_{e_i}} = FP_T(x_j) - \lambda_{e_j} + \lambda_{e_i},$$

where the last equality is due to the fact that only x_i descends from e_i and only x_j descends from e_j , and thus $D_{e_i} = D_{e_j} = 1$. Analogously, we have

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j) - \widetilde{\lambda}_{e_j} + \widetilde{\lambda}_{e_i},$$

where $\widetilde{\lambda}_e$ corresponds to the lengths of the respective pendant edges in \tilde{T} . However, as the entire cherry $[x_i, x_j]$ is preserved in \tilde{T} , we know that $\lambda_{e_i} = \widetilde{\lambda}_{e_i}$ and $\lambda_{e_j} = \widetilde{\lambda}_{e_j}$. This is due to the fact that as e_i does not get deleted from T to \tilde{T} , e_j does not get merged with the edge leading from the parent of w to w , so both edges remain unchanged. Thus, in total we have

$$FP_T(x_i) - FP_T(x_j) = \lambda_{e_i} - \lambda_{e_j} = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i) - FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j). \quad (1)$$

Without loss of generality, we assume that $FP_T(x_i) > FP_T(x_j)$ in π_T (as π_T is strict), which implies that $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j) > FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i)$ in $\pi_{\tilde{T}}$ (as π_T is reversible). However, this

9 implies both $FP_T(x_i) - FP_T(x_j) > 0$ and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i) - FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j) < 0$, which implies
 10 $FP_T(x_i) - FP_T(x_j) \neq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i) - FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j)$ and thus contradicts Equation (1). This
 11 completes the proof. □

12 *Proof of Theorem 2*

13 In order to prove Theorem 2, we need a few lemmas that state some properties of
 14 rankings and the FP index in general.

15 **Lemma 1** Let $T = (T_a, T_b)$ be a phylogenetic X -tree with maximal pendant subtrees T_a
 16 and T_b with taxon sets X_a and X_b , respectively. Let $X' \subset X$ be such that $X_a, X_b \not\subseteq X'$, i.e.
 17 neither X_a nor X_b are completely contained in X' . Moreover, let \tilde{T} be the induced subtree
 18 on $\tilde{X} = X \setminus X'$ resulting from T when the taxa of X' are deleted. Then, we have:
 19 $FP_T(x) \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all $x \in \tilde{X}$. Moreover, if $x' = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X} FP_T(x)$, and $X' \subset X$ is such
 20 that $x' \notin X'$ and the edge lengths of T are such that the deletion of X' induces a strict and
 21 reversible ranking π_T , then we have: $FP_T(x) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all $x \in \tilde{X} \setminus \{x'\}$ and
 22 $FP_T(x') \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x')$.

23 *Proof.* Let $x \in \tilde{X}$. Then, either the unique path from the root ρ of T to x contains at least
 24 one edge e that also occurs on one of the unique paths from ρ to taxa in X' or not. If not,
 25 then x is not affected by the deletion of X' at all, i.e. $FP_T(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ (note that this
 26 would not be true if we allowed X_a or X_b to be completely contained in X' , because then
 27 the deletion of the entire corresponding subtree would enforce a deletion of the edge
 28 leading to the other subtree and thus have an impact on the FP indices of the remaining
 29 taxa). However, if such an edge e exists, then a proportion of the edge length of e is
 30 assigned to x by the FP index. This proportion, however, increases when the taxa of X'
 31 are deleted, because then fewer leaves are descended from e and the FP index will account
 32 for this. As this holds for all such edges, in this case we have $FP_T(x) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$. Thus,
 33 altogether we have $FP_T(x) \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$. For the second part of the lemma, it only remains

34 to show that for all $x \neq x'$ the inequality is strict. Assume that it is not, i.e. assume that
 35 there is a $y \in \tilde{X} \setminus \{x'\}$ such that $FP_T(y) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(y)$. As $y \neq x'$ and as $x' = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X} FP_T(x)$
 36 and as π_T is strict and reversible, we know that $FP_T(y) < FP_T(x')$ and
 37 $FP_{\tilde{T}}(y) > FP_{\tilde{T}}(x')$. By Lemma 1 we have $FP_T(x') \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x')$. So in summary, this gives
 38 $FP_T(y) < FP_T(x') \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x') < FP_{\tilde{T}}(y) = FP_T(y)$. The latter equality is due to our
 39 assumption. So in summary, we have $FP_T(y) < FP_T(y)$. Clearly, this is a contradiction
 40 and therefore the assumption was wrong. This completes the proof. \square

41 **Lemma 2** Let T be a phylogenetic X -tree with $|X| = n$ and edge lengths $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \dots, \lambda_{2n-2}$.
 42 Let T' be like T , but with the edge lengths multiplied by k for some $k \in \mathbb{R}_+$, i.e. T' has
 43 edge lengths $\lambda_1 \cdot k, \lambda_2 \cdot k \dots, \lambda_{2n-2} \cdot k$. Then, we have: $FP_{T'}(x) = FP_T(x) \cdot k$ for all $x \in X$.
 44 In particular, we have $FP_T(x) > FP_T(y) \Leftrightarrow FP_{T'}(x) > FP_{T'}(y)$ for $x, y \in X$.

45 *Proof.* Let $x \in X$. Then, by definition of FP , we have $FP_T(x) = \sum_{e \in P(T; \rho, x)} \frac{\lambda_e}{D_e}$ and
 46 $FP_{T'}(x) = \sum_{e \in P(T'; \rho, x)} \frac{k \cdot \lambda_e}{D_e} = k \cdot \sum_{e \in P(T; \rho, x)} \frac{\lambda_e}{D_e} = k \cdot FP_T(x)$. For $k \in \mathbb{R}_+$, this immediately
 47 implies $FP_T(x) > FP_T(y) \Leftrightarrow FP_{T'}(x) = k \cdot FP_T(x) > k \cdot FP_T(y) = FP_{T'}(y)$. This
 48 completes the proof. \square

Lemma 3 Let T be a phylogenetic X -tree with $|X| = n$ and edge lengths $\lambda_T(e)$ for
 $e \in E(T)$. Let T' be like T , but such that the edge lengths of all pendant edges are longer
 by a constant $d \in \mathbb{R}_+$. More precisely, for all edge lengths $\lambda_{T'}(e)$ of edges e of T' , let

$$\lambda_{T'}(e) = \begin{cases} \lambda_T(e) + d & \text{if } e \text{ is a pendant edge of } T \text{ and } T', \\ \lambda_T(e) & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

49 Then, we have $FP_{T'}(x) = FP_T(x) + d$ and $FP_T(x) > FP_T(y) \Leftrightarrow FP_{T'}(x) > FP_{T'}(y)$ for all
 50 $x, y \in X$.

51 *Proof.* Let $x \in X$ and $d \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Let p_x denote the parent of x and let $e_x = (p_x, x)$ be the
 52 pendant edge incident to x . Then, by definition of FP , we have $FP_T(x) = \sum_{e \in P(T; \rho, x)} \frac{\lambda_T(e)}{D_e}$
 53 and $FP_{T'}(x) = \sum_{e \in P(T'; \rho, x)} \frac{\lambda_{T'}(e)}{D_e} = \sum_{e \in P(T'; \rho, p_x)} \frac{\lambda_{T'}(e)}{D_e} + \frac{\lambda_{T'}(e_x)}{1} = \sum_{e \in P(T; \rho, p_x)} \frac{\lambda_T(e)}{D_e} + \lambda_T(e_x) + d =$

54 $FP_T(x) + d$. This completes the first part of the proof. Now let $x, y \in X$ and $d \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Then
 55 we have: $FP_T(x) > FP_T(y) \Leftrightarrow FP_{T'}(x) = FP_T(x) + d > FP_T(y) + d = FP_{T'}(y)$. This
 56 completes the proof. \square

57 **Corollary 1** Let T be a phylogenetic X -tree with $|X| = n$. Let $\lambda_T(e)$ for $e \in E(T)$ be an
 58 edge length assignment for T that induces a strict and reversible ranking π_T concerning
 59 the deletion of some taxa $X' \subset X$. Let $d, k \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Then, if we multiply all edge lengths by
 60 k and subsequently add d to pendant edge lengths, the resulting branch lengths induce a
 61 strict and reversible ranking concerning the deletion of X' , too.

62 *Proof.* By Lemmas 2 and 3, the ranking π_T of the taxa in X induced by FP_T is not
 63 affected by scaling all branch lengths by k or adding d to the pendant edges. So we only
 64 need to show that the same is true for the ranking $\pi_{\tilde{T}}$ of the taxa in $\tilde{X} := X \setminus X'$.
 65 However, note that in \tilde{T} (i.e. in the subtree remaining when the taxa in X' get deleted),
 66 due to the suppression of degree-2 vertices, some edges get merged, but as both have been
 67 scaled by the same factor k , this also holds for the new long edge. For instance, if edges e_1
 68 and e_2 get merged, the scaling leads to two edges $k \cdot \lambda_{e_1}$ and $k \cdot \lambda_{e_2}$ in T , but to a single
 69 edge of length $k \cdot \lambda_{e_1} + k \cdot \lambda_{e_2} = k \cdot (\lambda_{e_1} + \lambda_{e_2})$ in \tilde{T} . So the edges in \tilde{T} get scaled by the
 70 same factor as the edges in T . In particular, by Lemma 2, this does not affect their
 71 ranking. Moreover, if we subsequently add d to the pendant edges of T , this also adds d to
 72 the pendant edges of \tilde{T} (regardless of whether these edges are merged with some inner
 73 edges or not). Thus, by Lemma 3, this again does not affect the ranking induced by $FP_{\tilde{T}}$,
 74 which completes the proof. \square

75 **Lemma 4** Let T be a phylogenetic X -tree with $|X| = n > 2$. Let \tilde{T} be the tree resulting
 76 from T when precisely one leaf from each cherry of T is deleted (and the resulting vertex
 77 with in-degree 1 and out-degree 1 is suppressed, respectively). Then, \tilde{T} has at least two
 78 leaves.

79 *Proof.* Let c_T denote the number of cherries in T . Clearly, $c_T \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, because if n is even,
80 at most *all* leaves can be contained in a cherry, in which case there are $\frac{n}{2}$ cherries, and if n
81 is odd, at most $n - 1$ leaves can be contained in cherries, in which case there are $\frac{n-1}{2}$
82 cherries. So if we now delete one leaf per cherry, this implies we delete $c_T \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ leaves.
83 Thus, for the number $n_{\tilde{T}}$ of leaves in \tilde{T} we have: $n_{\tilde{T}} = n - c_T \geq n - \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor \geq n - \frac{n}{2} = \frac{n}{2} > 1$.
84 The latter inequality is due to the fact that $n > 2$ by assumption. So we have that \tilde{T} has
85 more than one leaf; so it must have at least two leaves. This completes the proof. \square

86 *Proof of Theorem 2.* We prove the statement by induction on n . If $n = 2$, there is only
87 one rooted binary tree shape, namely the one that consists only of a cherry, say $[x_1, x_2]$ and
88 pendant edges e_1 and e_2 with edge lengths λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively. Then, $FP_T(x_1) = \lambda_1$
89 and $FP_T(x_2) = \lambda_2$. We choose $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 > 0$. So if we now delete leaf x_2 , which has minimal
90 FP_T value, we derive a tree \tilde{T} that only has one leaf x_1 . So x_1 , the leaf that formerly had
91 maximum FP_T value, is still present, and – because it is the only leaf – it has minimum
92 $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ value. This completes the base case of the induction.

93 Now assume the statement holds for all trees with at most $n - 1$ leaves and let
94 $T = (T_a, T_b)$ be a tree with n leaves. We now distinguish between two cases:

95 (i) T_b consists of only one leaf, i.e. $n_b = 1$. We may assume that x_n is the unique vertex
96 in T_b and so T looks as depicted in Figure 1. Note that in this case, all cherries of T
97 are actually contained in T_a . Then by the inductive hypothesis, as T_a has strictly
98 fewer leaves than T , there exist edge lengths for T_a that induce a strict and reversible
99 ranking π_{T_a} which fulfills all requirements stated by the theorem. We fix these edge
100 lengths accordingly and calculate $FP_{T_a}(x_1), \dots, FP_{T_a}(x_{n-1})$. Without loss of
101 generality, we have

$$FP_{T_a}(x_1) > FP_{T_a}(x_2) > \dots > FP_{T_a}(x_{n-1}). \quad (2)$$

102 In particular, we may assume $FP_{T_a}(x_1) = \max_{x \in X_a} \{FP_{T_a}(x)\}$ (otherwise, we could relabel
103 the taxa of T accordingly). As π_{T_a} is reversible by assumption and as \tilde{T}_a contains

Fig. 1. Tree T in part 1 of the proof of Theorem 2. In this case, T_b consists of only one vertex, and all cherries of T are contained in T_a .

104 taxon $x_1 = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(x)$, this immediately leads to

$$FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(\widetilde{x}_2) < \dots < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(\widetilde{x}_{n-1-c_T}), \quad (3)$$

105 where c_T denotes the number of cherries in T (and T_a) and thus the number of
 106 deleted leaves. Moreover, we know by assumption that $x_1 \in \widetilde{X}_a$, and we refer to the
 107 other elements of \widetilde{X}_a as $\widetilde{x}_2, \dots, \widetilde{x}_{n-1-c_T}$.

108 Note that we know (as ranking π_{T_a} is reversible) that $FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(\widetilde{x}_i) < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(\widetilde{x}_j)$ if and
 109 only if $i < j$. This means that the subset that remains when one leaf per cherry is
 110 deleted from T_a equals $\widetilde{X}_a = \{x_1, \widetilde{x}_2, \dots, \widetilde{x}_{n-1-c_T}\} \subset X_a$ and that the elements of \widetilde{X}_a
 111 are strictly reversed by $FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}$ compared to FP_{T_a} .

112 We now use ranking π_{T_a} to construct the desired ranking π_T . Therefore, note that
 113 $FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n-1}$ for all $x = x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}$. Using (2), this immediately leads to

$$FP_T(x_1) > FP_T(x_2) > \dots > FP_T(x_{n-1}). \quad (4)$$

114 Note that we also know that \widetilde{X}_a does *not* contain taxon x_{n-1} as π_{T_a} fulfills all
 115 requirements of the theorem by the inductive hypothesis, so $x_{n-1} = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(x)$
 116 has to be affected by the cherry leaf deletion.

117 Next, by Lemma 1, the deletion of one leaf per cherry can only further increase the
 118 FP index of a taxon in T_a or not change it at all, but it cannot decrease it, so we

119 have $FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x) \geq FP_{T_a}(x)$ for all $x \in \widetilde{X}_a$. Moreover, none of these deletions can affect
 120 T_b , as this subtree consists only of one leaf, which on its path to the root of T does
 121 not share an edge with any of the leaves of T_a . So we have

$$FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n-1-c_T} = FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x) > FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n-1} \text{ for all } x \in \widetilde{X}_a. \quad (5)$$

122 Here, the strict inequality is due to the fact that $FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x) \geq FP_{T_a}(x)$ and
 123 $\frac{\lambda_a}{n-1-c_T} > \frac{\lambda_a}{n-1}$ for all $x \in \widetilde{X}_a$, as $c_T \geq 1$. Moreover, we have $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_n) = FP_T(x_n) = \lambda_b$.

124 Combining Equations (3) and (5), we immediately get

$$FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1) < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(\widetilde{x}_2) < \dots < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(\widetilde{x}_{n-1-c_T}). \quad (6)$$

125 We now choose $\lambda_a > 0$ arbitrarily, e.g. $\lambda_a = 1$, and then want to choose λ_b such that
 126 $FP_T(x_n) = \lambda_b > FP_T(x_1)$ and $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_n) = \lambda_b < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1)$. By Equation (5), we have
 127 $FP_T(x_1) < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1)$, so we can simply choose λ_b between these two values. For
 128 instance, we can set $\lambda_b := FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\lambda_a}{n-1} + \frac{\lambda_a}{n-1-c_T} \right)$. This choice of λ_b is in the
 129 middle between $FP_T(x_1)$ and $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1)$. Therefore, using Equation (4) we now have:

$$\lambda_b = FP_T(x_n) > FP_T(x_1) > FP_T(x_2) > \dots > FP_T(x_{n-1}). \quad (7)$$

130 Moreover, using Equation (6), we immediately get:

$$\lambda_b = FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_n) < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1) < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(\widetilde{x}_2) < \dots < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(\widetilde{x}_{n-1-c_T}). \quad (8)$$

131 Therefore, we have found a strict and reversible ranking for T with respect to \widetilde{T} .

132 Moreover, we know that taxon x_n has maximal FP index in T , i.e.

133 $x_n = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X} FP_T(x)$, and x_n is contained in \widetilde{X} . Together with the fact that taxon
 134 x_{n-1} , which was deleted from X_a to get \widetilde{X}_a and which has the lowest FP_{T_a} value by
 135 (2) and thus also the lowest FP_T value by (4), is *not* contained in \widetilde{X} , this completes
 136 the first part of the proof.

Fig. 2. Tree T with the depicted edge lengths leads to

$FP_T(x_1) = 14.5 > FP_T(x_2) = 12.5 > FP_T(x_3) = 10.5 > FP_T(x_4) = 8.5$. We then construct \tilde{T} by deleting leaves x_2 and x_4 . This leads to $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_1) = 15 < 18 = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_3)$. This shows that the ranking π_T induced by the depicted edge lengths is strict and reversible. Note that leaf x_1 with the highest FP_T value is still present after the deletion, while leaf x_4 with the lowest FP_T value is amongst the deleted ones.

137 (ii) We now consider the case where both T_a and T_b contain at least two leaves each, i.e.
 138 $|X_a| = n_a \geq 2$ and $|X_b| = n_b \geq 2$ and $n_a \geq n_b$. In particular, this implies that both T_a
 139 and T_b have at least one cherry and are thus affected by the described leaf deletion
 140 (one leaf per cherry). In the following, let c_a and c_b denote the numbers of cherries of
 141 T_a and T_b , respectively. As n_a and n_b are both strictly smaller than n , for T_a and T_b
 142 we know by induction that there are edge lengths that allow for strict and reversible
 143 rankings π_{T_a} and π_{T_b} that fulfill all requirements stated by the theorem. We use these
 144 rankings to construct a strict and reversible ranking π_T for T .

145 We first consider the case where $n_a = 2$. As $2 = n_a \geq n_b \geq 2$, this immediately
 146 implies $n_b = 2$. Then, T looks as depicted in Figure 2, and we choose the edge lengths
 147 as given in that Figure. The caption of this figure explains why the depicted edge
 148 lengths lead to a strict and reversible ranking which fulfills all requirements of the
 149 theorem. So for $n_a = 2$, there remains nothing to show.

150 Thus, we may assume from now on that $n_a > 2$. By Lemma 4, we may conclude that
 151 when we delete one leaf from each cherry of T_a to obtain \tilde{T}_a , \tilde{T}_a still has at least two
 152 leaves, say x_1 and x_2 .

153 We now consider the rankings π_{T_a} and π_{T_b} and slightly modify the edge lengths for T_a
 154 and T_b , but such that the resulting induced rankings remain in the exact same order

as suggested by π_{T_a} and π_{T_b} :

- We multiply all edges of T_b by a factor $s_b > 0$. The resulting edge lengths still induce a strict and reversible ranking by Corollary 1, and this ranking has the same properties as π_{T_b} in the sense that it still fulfills all requirements of the theorem.
- We then add a constant $d_b > 0$ to all pendant edges of T_b . The resulting edge lengths still induce a strict and reversible ranking by Corollary 1. Again, this ranking has the same properties as π_{T_b} in the sense that it still fulfills all requirements of the theorem.
- We add a constant $d_a > 0$ to all pendant edges of T_a . Again, the resulting edge lengths still induce a strict and reversible ranking by Corollary 1 and still fulfill all requirements of the theorem.

Let λ_a denote the length of the edge leading from the root of T to T_a , and let λ_b denote the length of the edge leading from the root of T to T_b . Then, T now looks as depicted in Figure 3, and the FP indices of the leaves of T are as follows:

$$FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a} \text{ for all } x \in X_a, \text{ and} \quad (9)$$

$$FP_T(x) = FP_{T_b}(x) \cdot s_b + d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} \text{ for all } x \in X_b. \quad (10)$$

Now we delete all leaves from cherries of T that had to be deleted from T_a and T_b to get to the strict and reversible rankings π_{T_a} and π_{T_b} we started with. Assume this implies that we delete c_a cherry leaves from T_a and c_b cherry leaves from T_b . This results in tree $\tilde{T} = (\tilde{T}_a, \tilde{T}_b)$ with leaf set \tilde{X} , where the leaf sets of \tilde{T}_a and \tilde{T}_b are denoted by \tilde{X}_a and \tilde{X}_b , respectively.

Similarly as above, we can now express $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all taxa $x \in \tilde{X}$:

Fig. 3. Tree T with edge lengths based on the edge lengths of T_a and T_b that allow for a strict and reversible ranking, but with the modifications described in the second part of the inductive step in the proof of Theorem 2: Subtree T_b is scaled by a factor $s_b > 0$ (i.e. all edge lengths in T_b are multiplied by s_b). Then, all pendant edges in T_b are increased by a constant $d_b > 0$. Last, all pendant edges in T_a are increased by a constant $d_a > 0$.

$$FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x) = FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a} \text{ for all } x \in \widetilde{X}_a, \text{ and} \quad (11)$$

$$FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x) = FP_{\widetilde{T}_b}(x) \cdot s_b + d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b} \text{ for all } x \in \widetilde{X}_b. \quad (12)$$

Now, by Equations (10) and (12) it is clear that as $s_b \rightarrow 0$, we have

$$FP_T(x) \rightarrow d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} \text{ and } FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x) \rightarrow d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b} \text{ for all } x \in X_b.$$

Now, as stated above, we may assume that \widetilde{T}_a has at least two leaves. So now let x_1 ,

x_2 be two leaves from T_a which are also both present in \widetilde{T}_a and for which we have

$FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2)$ such that there is *no* taxon y in \widetilde{T}_a such that

$FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(y) < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2)$ (i.e. x_1 and x_2 are direct neighbors in the ranking

induced by $FP_{\widetilde{T}}$). Moreover, as π_{T_a} is strict and reversible by the inductive

hypothesis, we have $FP_{T_a}(x_1) > FP_{T_a}(x_2)$.

The high-level idea now is to perform the following two steps:

- First, we show that we can choose suitable values for d_a , d_b , λ_a and λ_b such that the limits of $FP_T(x)$ and $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x)$ for $s_b \rightarrow 0$ lie in the open intervals $(FP_T(x_2), FP_T(x_1))$ and $(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1), FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2))$, respectively. In particular, we will

show that all variables can be chosen such that $d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b}$ is precisely in the middle of the first interval and $d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}$ is precisely in the middle of the latter.

- We then show that, exploiting the first step, we can choose a value of $s_b > 0$ small enough to guarantee that *all* FP_T values of $x \in X_b$ are strictly contained in the first interval, and *all* $FP_{\widetilde{T}}$ values of $x \in X_b$ are strictly contained in the latter.

Now we proceed as follows:

- We set $\lambda_a := 1$.

- We introduce an auxiliary variable f and set

$$f := \underbrace{FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) - FP_{T_a}(x_1)}_{\geq 0 \text{ by Lemma 1}} + \underbrace{FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) - FP_{T_a}(x_2)}_{> 0 \text{ by Lemma 1}} > 0.$$

- Set $\lambda_b := \left(\frac{1}{2}f + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)}\right) \frac{n_b(n_b - c_b)}{c_b}$. Note that as $f, n_a, n_b, c_a, c_b > 0$ and $n_a > c_a$ and $n_b > c_b$, we have $\lambda_b > 0$.

- We introduce another auxiliary variable t and set

$$t := \frac{1}{2}f \frac{n_b - c_b}{c_b} + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)} \cdot \frac{n_b - c_b}{c_b} - \frac{1}{n_a} - \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) - \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2).$$

- Set $d_a := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t < 0 \\ t + 1 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$

Note that by this choice of d_a , we can guarantee both that $d_a > 0$ and $d_a > t$.

- Set $d_b := \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} - \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b}$. We need to show that $d_b > 0$.

In order to do so, we first substitute the chosen value for λ_b into the definition of d_b and get:

$$d_b = \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} - \frac{1}{n_b} \underbrace{\left(\left(\frac{1}{2}f + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)} \right) \frac{n_b(n_b - c_b)}{c_b} \right)}_{=\lambda_b}. \quad (13)$$

This term is larger than 0 if and only if

$$d_a > \left(\frac{1}{2}f + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)} \right) \frac{n_b - c_b}{c_b} - \frac{1}{n_a} - \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) - \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2). \text{ However, as the}$$

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right-hand side of the latter inequality equals t and as $d_a > t$ as shown above,

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this proves that indeed $d_b > 0$.

So with these values of λ_a , λ_b , d_a and d_b , we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} &\stackrel{(13)}{=} \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} \\
 &= FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(FP_{T_a}(x_1) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} \right) - \left(FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} \right) \right) \\
 &\stackrel{(9)}{=} FP_T(x_2) + \frac{1}{2} (FP_T(x_1) - FP_T(x_2)),
 \end{aligned}$$

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where the last equation uses $\lambda_a = 1$.

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Thus, $d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b}$ is precisely the middle of the interval $(FP_T(x_2), FP_T(x_1))$.

Analogously, again using $\lambda_a = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b} &\stackrel{(9)}{=} \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} - \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b} \\
&= \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} + \lambda_b \frac{c_b}{n_b(n_b - c_b)} \\
&= \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} \\
&\quad + \underbrace{\left(\left(\frac{1}{2}f + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)} \right) \frac{n_b(n_b - c_b)}{c_b} \right)}_{=\lambda_b} \frac{c_b}{n_b(n_b - c_b)} \\
&= \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)} + \frac{1}{2}f \\
&= \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{T_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} + \frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\left(FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) - FP_{T_a}(x_1) + FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) - FP_{T_a}(x_2) \right)}_{=f} \\
&= \frac{1}{2}FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a} + \underbrace{\left(\frac{1}{n_a - c_a} - \frac{1}{n_a} \right)}_{=\frac{c_a}{n_a(n_a - c_a)}} \\
&= \frac{1}{2}FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2}FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a - c_a} \\
&= FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a - c_a} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a - c_a} \right) - \left(FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_1) + d_a + \frac{1}{n_a - c_a} \right) \right) \\
&\stackrel{(11)}{=} FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1) + \frac{1}{2} \left(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2) - FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

213 Thus, $d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}$ is precisely the middle of the interval $(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1), FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2))$.

214 In total, this implies by Equations (10) and (12) that for a small enough value of
215 $s_b > 0$, all taxa $x \in X_b$ will have $FP_T(x)$ in the interval $(FP_T(x_2), FP_T(x_1))$ as well
216 as $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x)$ in the interval $(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1), FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2))$.

217 However, in order for our proof to be entirely constructive, we now show how to find
218 such values of s_b . Therefore, first note that by Equations (10) and (12) we know that

$FP_T(x)$ and $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x)$ for all $x \in X_b$ are strictly larger than the middle of their respective intervals $(FP_T(x_2), FP_T(x_1))$ and $(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1), FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2))$. So we only have to make sure that these values do not get larger than the upper bound of these intervals. Now, let $x_3, x_4 \in X_b$ be as follows: $x_3 = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X_b} FP_{T_b}(x)$ and $x_4 = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in \widetilde{X}_b \subseteq X_b} FP_{\widetilde{T}_b}(x)$. This means that x_3 has the highest possible FP_{T_b} value and x_4 has the highest $FP_{\widetilde{T}_b}$ value. So if we ensure that these two maxima are still smaller than the upper bounds of the intervals $(FP_T(x_2), FP_T(x_1))$ and $(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1), FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2))$, respectively, this will complete the proof.

So we need to choose $s_b > 0$ such that $FP_T(x_3) < FP_T(x_1)$ and $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_4) < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2)$. The first inequality holds if and only if $FP_{T_b}(x_3) \cdot s_b + d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} < FP_{T_a}(x_1) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a}$ (recall, however, that we set $\lambda_a = 1$). Using our above choice of d_b , it is easy to see that this holds if and only if

$$s_b < \frac{FP_{T_a}(x_1) - FP_{T_a}(x_2)}{2FP_{T_b}(x_3)}. \quad (14)$$

Note that the right-hand side of this inequality is strictly positive as we have $FP_{T_a}(x_1) > FP_{T_a}(x_2)$ by assumption.

However, as explained above, we also need $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_4) < FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2)$. This holds precisely if $FP_{\widetilde{T}_b}(x_4) \cdot s_b + d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b} < FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a}$. Without further simplifying this term using our choices of variables from above, we now simply note that the latter inequality holds if and only if

$$s_b < \frac{FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a} - d_b - \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}}{FP_{\widetilde{T}_b}(x_4)}. \quad (15)$$

We now need to show that the right-hand side of Equation (15) is strictly positive. This is true if and only if $FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a} > d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}$. However, recall that $d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}$ is the middle of the interval $(FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_1), FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2))$, so it is strictly smaller than the upper bound of this interval, which is why we have $FP_{\widetilde{T}}(x_2) > d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}$. In particular, this implies the desired inequality $FP_{\widetilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a} > d_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}$ as both d_a and $\frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a}$ are larger than 0.

Now we introduce an auxiliary variable m and let

$$m := \min \left\{ \frac{FP_{T_a}(x_1) - FP_{T_a}(x_2)}{2FP_{T_b}(x_3)}, \frac{FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x_2) + d_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - c_a} - d_b - \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b - c_b}}{FP_{\tilde{T}_b}(x_4)} \right\},$$

where $\lambda_a, \lambda_b, d_a$ and d_b are chosen as above. Then, $m > 0$, and we can take any value from the open interval $(0, m)$ as possible values for s_b . For instance, we can simply choose $s_b := \frac{1}{2}m$. By the definition of m , this will fulfill both (14) and (15), and it will still be positive, which means this value of s_b is a valid scaling factor for the edge lengths in T_b .

Now that we have chosen all edge lengths of T by downscaling T_b and extending the pendant edge lengths of T_a by constant d_a and those of the scaled version of T_b by constant d_b , we have achieved that the FP_T values of all $x \in X_b$ are in between $FP_T(x_2)$ and $FP_T(x_1)$ in the exact order induced by π_{T_b} . Analogously, the $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ values of all $x \in X_b$ are in between $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_1)$ and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2)$ in the exact order induced by π_{T_b} . Moreover, the FP_T and $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ values of all $x \in X_a$ behave exactly as induced by π_{T_a} . Therefore, these edge lengths are in total such that the derived ranking is strict and reversible.

Next, we argue why this strict and reversible ranking is such that the taxon with the highest FP_T value is still contained in \tilde{T} , while the taxon with the smallest FP_T value is not. Note that π_{T_a} is strict and reversible and fulfills all requirements of the theorem by the inductive hypothesis. So the leaf deletion used to reverse the ranking of FP_{T_a} does not affect leaf x with $x = \operatorname{argmax}_{y \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(y)$, while the deletion of leaf y with $y = \operatorname{argmin}_{z \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(z)$ is ensured. So leaf x is also still present in \tilde{T} while y is not. Moreover, x must have maximal FP_T value and y must have minimal FP_T value, because the FP_T value of all leaves of T_b are now by construction between $FP_T(x_1)$ and $FP_T(x_2)$ and can therefore neither be maximal nor minimal for T . So the maximal leaf of T_a must be the maximal leaf of T and the minimal leaf of T_a must also be the minimal leaf of T , as $FP_T(u) > FP_T(v) \Leftrightarrow FP_{T_a}(u) > FP_{T_a}(v)$ for all $u, v \in X_a$ by Equation (9). This completes the proof.

□

Proof of Theorem 3

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In order to prove Theorem 3, we require two more lemmas.

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Lemma 5 Let $T = (T_a, T_b)$ be a binary phylogenetic X -tree with $|X| = n \geq 2$. Let \tilde{T} be a tree that results from T by deleting some, but *not all*, leaves from T_a (or T_b) only. Then, we have:

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(i) $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) = FP_T(x)$ for all $x \in T_b$ (or T_a , respectively).

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(ii) $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) > FP_T(x)$ for all $x \in T_a$ (or T_b , respectively).

Proof. Let $T = (T_a, T_b)$ and \tilde{T} be as described in the lemma. Assume without loss of generality that the deleted leaf set X' is a strict subset of the taxon set X_a of T_a . Let \tilde{T}_a and \tilde{T}_b be the trees that result from T_a and T_b , respectively when the leaves of $X' \subset X_a$ are deleted, and denote by λ_b the length of the edge leading to T_b in T and by n_b the number of leaves in T_b . Then, $FP_T(x) = FP_{T_b}(x) + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b}$ and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}_b}(x) + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b}$ for all $x \in X_b$. However, as no leaf from T_b got deleted and not all leaves from T_a have been deleted so that the edge leading to T_b does not get suppressed, we have $\tilde{T}_b = T_b$, which shows that $FP_T(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all $x \in X_b$. This completes the proof of the first statement. For the second statement, denote by $\kappa_a := |X'| > 0$ the number of deleted leaves. As $X' \subset X_a$, we have $\kappa_a < n_a$, where n_a denotes the number of leaves in T_a . Moreover, let λ_a denote the length of the edge leading to T_a in T . Then, $FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a}$ and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - \kappa_a}$ for all $x \in X_a$. By Lemma 1 we have $FP_{T_a}(x) \leq FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x)$. So in total, this implies

$$FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a} < FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a - \kappa_a} = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x),$$

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where the strict inequality stems from the fact that $\kappa_a > 0$. This completes the proof. \square

278

Lemma 6 Let T be a phylogenetic tree on leaf set $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, and let

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$\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ be a vector of strictly positive values. Then, there exist strictly

280 positive edge lengths for T such that the induced FP indices equal θ , i.e. $FP_T(x_i) = \theta_i$ for
 281 all $i = 1, \dots, n$.

282 The statement of Lemma 6 is established in Wicke et al. (2020) (proof of Theorem
 283 2 therein). Note that Theorem 2 in Wicke et al. (2020) itself is phrased in a slightly
 284 different context, but in the proof it is shown that given a rooted phylogenetic X -tree with
 285 $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ and a vector $\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n) \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ of strictly positive real numbers, there
 286 exists an edge length assignment $\lambda : E(T) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ that assigns strictly positive lengths to all
 287 edges of T such that $\theta_i = FP_{(T,\lambda)}(x_i)$ for all $x_i \in X$.

288 *Proof of Theorem 3.* We prove this statement by induction on n . If $n = 2$, there is only
 289 one phylogenetic X -tree, namely the one that consists of a cherry, say $[x_1, x_2]$, and the
 290 statement trivially holds.

291 We now assume that the statement holds for all trees with at most $n - 1$ leaves and
 292 let $T = (T_a, T_b)$ be a tree with $n \geq 3$ leaves (else consider the base case). Without loss of
 293 generality we may assume that $n_a \geq n_b$. In particular, $n_a \geq 2$ (because $n \geq 3$). Moreover,
 294 we may assume that $X_a = \{x_1, \dots, x_{n_a}\}$ and $X_b = \{x_{n_a+1}, \dots, x_{n_a+n_b}\}$ (else, re-label the
 295 leaves of T accordingly).

296 As T_a is a phylogenetic tree with $n_a < n$ leaves, by the inductive hypothesis, there
 297 exist strictly positive edge lengths for T_a that satisfy all requirements stated by the
 298 theorem. We fix these edge lengths and additionally assign length $\lambda_a \in \mathbb{R}_+$ to edge (ρ, a)
 299 connecting T_a with the root of T . Then, $FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a}$ for all $x \in X_a$.

300 Without loss of generality, we may assume that $FP_{T_a}(x_1) = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(x)$ and
 301 $FP_{T_a}(x_2) = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_a \setminus \{x_1\}} FP_{T_a}(x)$ (else, re-label the leaves in T_a accordingly), i.e. leaves x_1 and
 302 x_2 have the lowest and second lowest FP_{T_a} value among the taxa in X_a , respectively.

303 Let \tilde{T} be the tree obtained from T by deleting leaf x_1 and let $\tilde{X} := X \setminus \{x_1\}$ denote
 304 the leaf set of \tilde{T} . Note that by the inductive hypothesis, $x_2 = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in \tilde{X}_a} FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x)$.

305 We now choose the edge lengths of T_b as well as the length λ_b of edge (ρ, b)
 306 connecting T_b with the root of T such that

307 $FP_T(x) \in (FP_{T_a}(x_2) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a}, FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x_2) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a-1}) = (FP_T(x_2), FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2))$ for all $x \in X_b$ and such
 308 that $FP_T(x_i) \neq FP_T(x_j)$ as well as $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i) \neq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j)$ for all $x_i \neq x_j \in \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$.

309 To see that this is possible, first note that $FP_T(x_2) \neq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2)$:

- If $n_a = 2$, i.e. x_1 and x_2 are the only leaves in T_a , we have

$$FP_T(x_2) = \lambda_{e_2} + \frac{\lambda_a}{2} \quad \text{and}$$

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2) = \lambda_{e_2} + \lambda_a > FP_T(x_2),$$

310 where λ_{e_2} denotes the length of the pendant edge incident with x_2 .

- If $n_a > 2$, then $FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x_2) \geq FP_{T_a}(x_2)$ by Lemma 1 and $\frac{\lambda_a}{n_a-1} > \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a}$. In particular,
 312 $FP_T(x_2) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2)$.

313 Thus, in both cases the interval $(FP_T(x_2), FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2))$ is non-empty and contains infinitely
 314 many strictly positive real numbers.

315 We now distinguish two cases:

- (a) If T_b consists of precisely one leaf, namely leaf x_n , we choose λ_b , which in this case
 317 equals $FP_T(x_n) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_n)$, in the interval $(FP_T(x_2), FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2))$, such that

318 $\lambda_b \neq FP_T(x)$ for all $x \in X_a$ and $\lambda_b \neq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all $x \in X_a$.

- (b) If T_b contains $n_b > 1$ leaves, we choose ε such that $0 < \frac{\varepsilon}{n_b} < FP_T(x_2)$ and set $\lambda_b = \varepsilon$.

320 We then choose n_b distinct strictly positive real values

321 $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{n_b} \in (FP_T(x_2) - \frac{\varepsilon}{n_b}, FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2) - \frac{\varepsilon}{n_b})$ such that $\theta_i \neq FP_T(x)$ for all i and all
 322 $x \in X_a$ and $\theta_i \neq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all i and all $x \in X_a$. Then, by Lemma 6 we can choose

323 strictly positive edge lengths for T_b such that the induced FP_{T_b} values for the leaves in

324 X_b (i.e. for leaves $x_{n_a+1}, \dots, x_{n_a+n_b}$) equal θ , i.e. $FP_{T_b}(x_{n_a+i}) = \theta_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, n_b$.

325 Now, by choice of θ_i and λ_b , this implies that

326 $FP_T(x_{n_a+i}) = FP_{T_b}(x_{n_a+i}) + \frac{\varepsilon}{n_b} \in (FP_T(x_2), FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2))$ for all $i \in \{1, \dots, n_b\}$.

327 Thus, in both cases, we can choose the edge lengths of T_b and the length of edge (ρ, b) such
 328 that $FP_T(x) \in (FP_T(x_2), FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2))$ for all $x \in X_b$ and such that the rankings π_T and $\pi_{\tilde{T}}$

329 are strict.

330 Now, as $FP_T(x) > FP_T(x_2)$ for all $x \in X_b$ by construction, and
 331 $FP_T(x_2) > FP_T(x_1)$ (because by the inductive hypothesis for T_a and the assumption that
 332 $x_1 = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(x)$, we have $FP_{T_a}(x_1) < FP_{T_a}(x_2)$ and thus also $FP_T(x_1) < FP_T(x_2)$),
 333 we can conclude that $x_1 = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X} FP_T(x)$. Similarly, as by assumption
 334 $x_2 = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_a \setminus \{x_1\}} FP_{T_a}(x)$, we can conclude that $x_2 = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in \tilde{X}} FP_T(x)$. Thus, leaves x_1 and x_2
 335 have the lowest, respectively second lowest FP_T value.

336 Moreover, as $FP_T(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2)$ for all $x \in X_b$ by construction (where
 337 the first equality follows from the fact that the FP indices of leaves in X_b are not affected
 338 by the deletion of leaf $x_1 \in X_a$; cf. Lemma 5, Part (i)) and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2)$ for all
 339 $x \in \tilde{X}_a$ by the inductive hypothesis (as $x_2 = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in \tilde{X}_a} FP_{\tilde{T}_a}(x)$ and thus in particular,
 340 $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2) > FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all $x \in X_a \setminus \{x_2\}$ because the ranking is strict), we can conclude
 341 that $x_2 = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in \tilde{X}} FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$, i.e. leaf x_2 has the largest $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ value.

342 Thus, we have shown that there are edge lengths for T such that if the leaf with the
 343 lowest FP_T value (in our case leaf x_1) is deleted, the leaf with the second lowest FP_T value
 344 (in our case leaf x_2) has the highest $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ value. Moreover, the corresponding rankings are
 345 strict. This completes the proof. \square

346 *Proof of Theorem 4*

347 *Proof of Theorem 4.* Let T , λ , x^* and x' be as stated in the theorem and let λ_a , λ_b denote
 348 the lengths of the edges leading to T_a and T_b , respectively. Note that if x' is in T_a , we have
 349 $FP_T(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ for all x in T_b by Lemma 5, Part (i). However, for all leaves x in T_a
 350 (other than the deleted x') we have $FP_T(x) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$ by Lemma 5, Part (ii). So
 351 depending on whether x' is in T_a or T_b , we have $n_a - 1$ or $n_b - 1$ leaves whose FP indices
 352 strictly increase when x' is deleted and all others remain unchanged. As x^* is the taxon
 353 with maximal FP_T value, the only taxa which can have a larger $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ value than x^* are the
 354 ones whose FP indices increases when x' is deleted, so these are at most $n_a - 1$ leaves (as

355 $n_a - 1 \geq n_b - 1$). Moreover, as $n_a \geq n_b$ and $n_a + n_b = n$, we have $n_a \geq \lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor$ and thus
 356 $n_a - 1 \geq \lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor - 1 = \lfloor \frac{n-1}{2} \rfloor$. This completes the first part of the proof.

For the second part of the proof we use Lemma 6 to assign positive edge lengths to T_a and T_b that induce strict rankings π_{T_a} and π_{T_b} . We denote by X_a and X_b the leaf sets of T_a and T_b , respectively. Then, we fix leaves $x_a^* := \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(x)$ and $x_b^* := \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in X_b} FP_{T_b}(x)$, i.e. x_a^* is the leaf with highest FP_{T_a} value and x_b^* is the leaf with highest FP_{T_b} value. Similarly, we fix leaves $x'_a := \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_a} FP_{T_a}(x)$ and $x'_b := \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in X_b} FP_{T_b}(x)$, i.e. x'_a is the leaf with smallest FP_{T_a} value and x'_b is the leaf with smallest FP_{T_b} value. We will now proceed as follows: Using Corollary 1, we scale T_a and T_b by positive scaling factors s_a and s_b , respectively, such that the rankings induced by π_{T_a} and π_{T_b} are not changed. If λ_a and λ_b denote the edge lengths of the edges leading from the root of T to T_a and T_b , respectively, we derive the following equalities:

$$FP_T(x) = FP_{T_a}(x) \cdot s_a + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a} \xrightarrow{s_a \rightarrow 0} \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a} \text{ for all } x \in X_a, \text{ and}$$

$$FP_T(x) = FP_{T_b}(x) \cdot s_b + \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} \xrightarrow{s_b \rightarrow 0} \frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} \text{ for all } x \in X_b.$$

357 Moreover, if we delete x'_a from T and thus from T_a to derive tree \tilde{T} , the FP indices
 358 of T_b remain completely unchanged by Lemma 5, Part (i), so we have $FP_T(x) = FP_{\tilde{T}}(x)$
 359 for all $x \in X_b$. However, the FP indices of *all* taxa of T_a strictly increase by Lemma 5, Part
 360 (ii), as the proportion of λ_a assigned to all leaves of T_a increases from $\frac{\lambda_a}{n_a}$ to $\frac{\lambda_a}{n_a-1}$ (and
 361 possibly the proportion of other edges within T_a that is assigned to taxa from T_a also gets
 362 higher, so we can only state the following lower bound for the $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ values), so we have:

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x) \geq FP_T(x) + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a(n_a-1)} \quad \forall x \in X_a \setminus \{x'_a\}. \quad (16)$$

363 The latter summand is due to the fact that $\frac{\lambda_a}{n_a-1} = \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a} + \frac{\lambda_a}{n_a(n_a-1)}$ for all $x \in X_a \setminus \{x'_a\}$.

364 The high-level idea is as follows: We want to choose positive values for λ_a , λ_b , s_a
 365 and s_b such that $FP_T(x'_b) > FP_T(x_a^*)$ and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_b^*) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_a)$ for all $x_a \in X_a \setminus \{x'_a\}$. Note
 366 that these inequalities imply that *all* leaves of T_b have higher FP_T values than the leaves

367 of T_a and that *all* leaves of T_b have lower $FP_{\tilde{T}}$ values than the leaves of T_a (other than x'_a).

- 368 • We start by setting $\lambda_a := 1$.
- 369 • Next, we set $\lambda_b := \frac{(2n_a-1)n_b}{2n_a(n_a-1)}$. Note that $\lambda_b > 0$ as $n \geq 3$ and thus $n_a > 1$.
- 370 • We set $s_b := \frac{n_b - \lambda_b(n_a-1)}{2FP_{T_b}(x_b^*) \cdot n_b(n_a-1)}$. We now show that this ensures that $s_b > 0$. First, as
 371 before we have $n_a > 1$ (because $n \geq 3$), so the denominator is positive. Moreover, we
 372 have $n_b - \lambda_b(n_a - 1) = n_b - \frac{(2n_a-1)n_b}{2n_a(n_a-1)}(n_a - 1) = n_b \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2n_a-1}{2n_a}\right) = \frac{n_b}{2n_a} > 0$, so the
 373 enumerator is also positive. Thus, $s_b > 0$.
- Last, we set $s_a := \frac{1}{2FP_{T_a}(x_a^*)} \left(\frac{\lambda_b}{n_b} - \frac{1}{n_a}\right)$. We now show that $s_a > 0$. Note that this is true precisely if $\lambda_b > \frac{n_b}{n_a}$. Using our choice of λ_b , this holds if and only if

$$\frac{(2n_a - 1)n_b}{2n_a(n_a - 1)} > \frac{n_b}{n_a},$$

374 which in turn holds precisely if

$$\frac{2n_a - 1}{2(n_a - 1)} > 1.$$

375 As $2n_a - 1 > 2n_a - 2$, the assertion holds and we therefore indeed have $s_a > 0$.

376 The fact that these choices of variables indeed work, i.e. that for these values of λ_a ,
 377 λ_b , s_a and s_b we have $FP_T(x'_b) > FP_T(x_a^*)$ and $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_b^*) < FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_a)$ for all $x_a \in X_a \setminus \{x'_a\}$,
 378 can be shown in a similar manner as in the proof of Theorem 2, which is why we omit the
 379 details here for brevity. □

380 *Proof of Proposition 1*

Proof of Proposition 1. Let T be an ultrametric caterpillar tree on $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ with $n \geq 3$. Without loss of generality we may assume that the leaf labels and edge lengths of T are as indicated in Figure 4. In particular, the length of the pendant edge incident to x_1 is λ_1 , and for each x_j with $j = 2, \dots, n$, the length of the pendant edge incident to x_j is equal

to $\sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \lambda_k$ (due to the fact that T is ultrametric). Moreover, the number of leaves below an interior edge of length λ_j is equal to j for $j = 2, \dots, n-1$. Thus,

$$FP_T(x_1) = \lambda_1 + \sum_{k=2}^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_k}{k},$$

and for $j = 2, \dots, n$,

$$FP_T(x_j) = \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \lambda_k + \sum_{k=j}^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_k}{k}.$$

This directly implies

$$FP_T(x_1) \leq FP_T(x_2) \leq FP_T(x_3) \leq \dots \leq FP_T(x_{n-1}) \leq FP_T(x_n).$$

381 (In fact, we have $FP_T(x_1) = FP_T(x_2)$, whereas all other inequalities are strict.) Now,
382 suppose that a single element $x_i \in X'$ is deleted from T to obtain \tilde{T} .

- If $x_i = x_n$, \tilde{T} is a caterpillar tree on $\{x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}\}$ with the parent of x_{n-1} being the root. Analogously to the calculations above it now follows that

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_1) \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_2) \leq \dots \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_{n-1}).$$

383 In particular, the ranking order of the elements in \tilde{X} on \tilde{T} is identical to the
384 respective ranking order on T .

- If $x_i \neq x_n$, \tilde{T} is a caterpillar tree on $\tilde{X} = X \setminus \{x_i\}$ obtained from T by deleting x_i and its incident edge and suppressing the resulting degree-2 vertex. Without loss of generality we can assume that $x_i \neq x_1$ (otherwise switch the labels of x_1 and x_2) and we have

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_1) = \lambda_1 + \sum_{k=2}^{i-2} \frac{\lambda_k}{k} + \frac{\lambda_{i-1} + \lambda_i}{i-1} + \sum_{k=i+1}^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_k}{k-1}. \quad (17)$$

For $2 \leq j \leq i-1$, we have

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j) = \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \lambda_k + \sum_{k=j}^{i-2} \frac{\lambda_k}{k} + \frac{\lambda_{i-1} + \lambda_i}{i-1} + \sum_{k=i+1}^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_k}{k-1}. \quad (18)$$

Finally, for $i + 1 \leq j \leq n$, we have

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j) = \sum_{k=1}^{j-1} \lambda_k + \sum_{k=j}^{n-1} \frac{\lambda_k}{k-1}. \tag{19}$$

Comparing Equations (17), (18), and (19), we clearly have

$$FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_1) \leq \dots \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_{i-1}) \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_{i+1}) \leq \dots \leq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_n).$$

385 In particular, if $FP_T(x_i) \geq FP_T(x_j)$, then we also have $FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_i) \geq FP_{\tilde{T}}(x_j)$ for all
 386 $x_i, x_j \in \tilde{X}$.

387 Now, if $|X'| > 1$, we sequentially delete all other elements of X' and repeat the argument
 388 above. This completes the proof.

Fig. 4. Ultrametric caterpillar tree T on $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ used in the proof of Proposition 1.

389 □

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